

CONDITIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF PRIMARY COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN CHILDREN WITHOUT SPEECH

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Abstract

Children's speech is a valuable voice of a specific child-related subculture. Speech development is not only a part of introducing the child to the world, but also a pillar of general mental development. The development of the child's speech is related to the formation of the personality as a whole and at the same time all mental processes.

Key words: development of oral speech, achievements of science and technology and technologies, formation of speech and thinking, physical development of children, non-speech.

Man, his all-round harmonious development, well-being, creation of conditions and effective mechanisms for the realization of personal interests, changing the patterns of outdated thinking and social behavior are the main goal and driving force of the reforms implemented in the republic. The formation of an excellent system of personnel training on the basis of the rich intellectual heritage of the people and universal human resources, on the basis of the achievements of modern culture, economy, science and technology, is an important condition for the development of Uzbekistan.

In our republic, preschool education has already risen to the level of state policy. Therefore, any problem related to the first link of the education system is solved at the state level. In particular, educators of the preschool education system today have a basic program for preparing children for school, as well as teaching-methodical materials that have been highly rated in the experimental-testing process. This program covers various issues such as physical development of children, formation of speech and thinking, introduction to the environment.

Currently, the search for the optimal form of organization of children's education, which allows to ensure the high level of mental and speech development of children, and the formation of their language skills, is being carried out. Questions about the content and forms of such training are resolved in theoretical and practical research.

It is difficult to overestimate the importance of language development in all aspects of a child's life. A strong argument can be made for the central role of communication and language as key to life skills. In the early years of formal education and school life, language skills based on effective verbal and non-verbal communication are the basis for learning and development. Growth in language and other important skills included reading, literacy and numeracy. In addition, the difficulty of communication and language development now is evidence of lifelong effects. Language skills are the best predictor of successful foreign education: language development in the first 2 years of elementary school predicts the characteristics of a child. Otherwise, difficulties in language learning are associated with educational failure: children with speech and language problems when they first step into school have the greatest difficulties with their literacy.

Individual abilities in speech development are expressed both in accessibility and in the pace of acquiring language and fluent speech. Many children like to comment on their actions and attract the attention of others. At the same time, the speech development of some children does not correspond to their practical activities, as a result, such a gifted child lags behind other children in the group. Less receptive children speak less, but usually perform practical tasks faster and more accurately than others.

Agreeing with the basic approach to the acquisition of speech by the child, we drew attention to the fact that the authors of the manual often use "help", "practice" and other expressions, but how to help, practice they pay little attention to what can be done.

Exercises that are not aimed at the development of speech may not have a positive effect on the development of children's connected speech. The analysis of psychological-pedagogical research in the field of speech development of preschool children and teaching them their mother tongue allows us to come to the following conclusions:

- Speech development is a very complex and multifactorial process related to the assimilation of socio-historical experience, which occupies a central place in the individual development of a child.
- It is not a spontaneous process, but a creative process that offers pedagogical guidance.

- A pedagogue managing the process of speech development of a child should know the laws, mechanisms and characteristics of this process at different age stages, be able to see the individual characteristics of speech development, and take into account the child's unique characteristics, the most effective way to influence the child's speech. must choose.
- The historically formed content of human experience is summarized in verbal form, and its description and mastering implies the participation of speech in this process. Speech opens the way for a child to all the achievements of human culture.
- The most important stages of acquiring speech correspond to preschool age.
- Pre-school education ensures a healthy, all-round development of a child, instills in him a desire to study, prepares him for regular education.
- In the process of gradually getting to know the words that a preschooler hears, understands their meaning, remembers and uses, through the information of his parents, peers, as well as his own words that are not too many he will find out based on his reserve.

There are periods in a person's life when it may be difficult to develop speech. This happens at the beginning of the second year - the child is interested in walking and "forgets" the conversation. Physically growing children also tend to neglect other skills such as speech. You have to wait for this time. After a few weeks, everything will be back to normal. The most important thing is to encourage the child to talk so that he does not get used to talking.

A child can communicate more or less. He understands everything, connects words with things, forms sentences and sentences. His vocabulary is quickly enriched and he tries to talk as much as possible. At this time, it is very important to ensure the correct pronunciation of all sounds. Of course, the "p" sound is very difficult to produce, and usually children start chasing it after a while.

What you can do: Continue to communicate with the child as an equal - he will appreciate it. For example, ask to perform complex tasks such as "fetch the book that is on the table". "Where is your favorite book?" Asking can complicate the task. He can find the child himself.

What worries: the child does not try to combine words into sentences. Continues to use only simple sounds, does not enrich the word.

If you are sure that your child listens and understands you, speech therapists confirm that there are no birth defects - give the child time. Take all stages of development calmly - children's speech is sometimes unpredictable. A child can be silent for up to three years, and then suddenly begins to speak with complex phrases and sentences. Most importantly, don't worry ahead of time and praise your child for doing well. Let him feel important and loved.

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